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MUNDARIJA

“Yashil” iqtisodiyotga jadal o‘tish va barqaror texnologik o‘zgarishlar provard maqsadlarimiz	12
Abduraxmonova Gulnora Kalandarovna	
Noqonuniy sigaretalar hajmini Empty pack survey hamda Gap analysis usullari yordamida aniqlash (O‘zbekiston Respublikasi misolida)	17
Sanjar Mirzaliev, Bobur Qoraboev, Surmaniso Mirzalieva	
Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida bank xizmat turlarini rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	22
A. R. Norov, N. N. Norova	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot rivojida tijorat banklari kapitalini takomillashtirish istiqbollari	28
Norov Akmal Ruzimamatovich	
Ishsizlik darajasini kamaytirish yo‘lidagi strategik yondashuv: tadbirkorlikka o‘rgatish va kasbiy tayyorlash	33
Bakiyeva Iroda Akbarovna, Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich	
Meva-sabzavot mahsulotlarini eksportga yo‘naltirishda standart talablariga uyg‘unlashtirishni baholash va uni amalga oshirish yo‘llari	42
Xojiyev Elshod Yoqub o‘g‘li	
Investitsiyalarni jalb qilishda foyda solig‘idan foydalanish	50
Zarif Oripovich Axrorov	
Mamlakat iqtisodiy o‘shish va rivojlanishida xorijiy investitsiyalarning roli	55
Akishova Shaxnoza Davlet qizi	
O‘zbekiston sharoitida “yashil” iqtisodiyotni joriy etish istiqbollari: nazariya va amaliyot.....	60
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o‘g‘li	
Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlari faoliyatini takomillashtirish yo‘nalishlari.....	65
Sadikova Muslima Alisher qizi	
Mehnat bozorida aholi bandligini oshirishning zamonaviy usullari	70
Xuvaydullaeva Iroda Xusniddin qizi	
Ichki turizmni rivojlantirishning tashkiliy mexanizmining asosiy prinsiplari	76
Isomiddinov Inomjon Qurbonali o‘g‘li	
Yengil sanoat korxonalarida ichki audit jarayonlari va uning samaradorligini oshirish istiqbollari.....	79
Maxmudov A.N.	
Ishlab chiqarish resurslaridan foydalangan holda korporativ boshqaruv tizimini takomillashtirish	86
Karimov Akramjon Ikromjon o‘g‘li	
Kredit foiz stavkalari va unga ta‘sir etuvchi omillar tahlili.....	92
Orifova Dilnoza Obid qizi	
O‘zbekistonda hayot sug‘urtasini rivojlantirish yo‘llari	97
Jamolova Xonzoda O‘rolboy qizi	
Soliqqa Tortishning Mohiyati va Uni Iqtisodiyotdagi Ahamiyati.....	102
Ruziyev Shaxzod Behzod o‘g‘li, Togayev Salim Sobirovich	
Raqamli texnologiyalarning oziq-ovqat sanoatini rivojlantirishdagi ta‘siri	110
Abduraxmanova Zuxra Toxir qizi	
O‘zbekistonda sog‘lomlashtirish turizmini rivojlantirishda inson resurslarining o‘rni.....	115
Shaymanova Nigora Yusupovna	
Biznes jarayonlarining samaradorligini baholash ko‘rsatkichlarini muvofiqlashtirish usullari.....	121
Abdusalomova Nodira Baxodirovna	

Turizmda inson resurslarini rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari.....	126
J. Mansurov	
Hududiy turizm rivojlanishining iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirishda zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalarini qo'llanilishi	131
Dustmurodov Orifjon Ismatilloevich	
Aholi ixtiyoridagi resurslarni jalb kilish orqali aholi turmush darajasini oshirish.....	138
Jo'raeva Shahlo Uchqun qizi	
Turistik xizmatlarning samaradorligini oshirishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish	141
Abduvohidov Abdumalik Mahkamovich	
Xo'jalik subyektlarining moliyaviy salohiyatini mustahkamlash va moliyaviy barqarorligini ta'minlashni uslubiy jihatlari.....	146
Xasanov Baxodir Akramovich, Akramov G'olibjon Bahodir o'g'li	
Mahsulot raqobatbardoshligini baholash usullari va ulardan foydalanish muammolari.	153
Onorboev Sh.M.	
Loyihalarni Islom modeli asosida moliyalashtirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	159
Aminova Nilufar Umarboy qizi	
O'zbekiston tijorat banklarida foiz riskini boshqarish tizimini takomillashtirish	167
Isakov Janabay Yakipbaevich	
Ayollar inson kapitalini rivojlantirishning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ahamiyati.....	174
S.A.Bozorova, M.M.Xolmatov	
Qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalarini yaratish bilan bog'liq loyihalarni moliyalashtirish	179
Shaislamova Nargiza Kabilovna	
Effectiveness of using blockchain technologies in cash flow audit in enterprises of the republic of Uzbekistan.....	188
Atamurodov Saidmurad Yakhyoyevich	
Loan portfolio of banks in Uzbekistan and ways to improve the efficiency of loan portfolio management.....	196
Avazkhon Agzamov, Dilrabo Malikova	
Digitization of the economy and its role in enhancing bank stability and reducing poverty	201
Kholiyorov Murod Kahramon ugli, Kholiyorova Shokhista Kahramon kizi	
Directions for sustainable development of tourism in the namangan region of Uzbekistan.....	204
Khusniddin Egamnazarov	
Improving comprehensive monitoring of cash flows in the treasury through intelligent information fusion systems applications.....	208
Shodmonkulova Shahlo	
Importance of staff service quality at uzbek halal restaurants in Uzbekistan	214
Shodiyona Sanginova	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida barqaror turizmni iqtisodiy rivojlantirishda hunarmandchilikning o'rni.....	220
Xushnazarova Maxzuna Gulamdjanovna	
Mamlakat turizmini barqaror rivojlanishida mice turizmining ahamiyati.....	226
Xalimova Fayyoza Nafasovna	
Ways to expand the position of the light industrial enterprise in the yarn and knitwear market.....	231
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Agzamov Avazkhon Talgatovich	
Improvement of methodology of accounting and analysis of included financial statements and investments in subsidiary societies	238
Nasirkhodjaeva Dilafruz Sabitkhanovna	

Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida investitsiyalar: barqaror iqtisodiy o'sishning muhim omili.....	254
Amonova Nazokat Uturovna	
O'zbekiston respublikasi korxonalarida pul oqimlari auditida blokchain texnologiyalaridan foydalanish samaradorligi.....	259
Atamurodov Saidmurod Yaxyoyevich	
Iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish sharoitida o'zbekistonda turizm xizmatlar iste'molini oshirishning ekonometrik tahlili	267
Dehqonov Burxon Rustamovich	
Agrar soha korxonalarining moliyaviy barqarorligini ta'minlash masalalari.....	278
Erkinxojiyev I.	
Yengil sanoat korxonalarida marketing jarayonlarini tashkil etishning xorij tajribasi	283
Bazarova Fayoza Tuxtamurodovna	
Fiskal siyosatni rivojlantirishda "yashil" budjet daromadlarini o'rganish.....	287
Meyliyev O.R., Gofurova K.	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot: raqamli transformatsiyaning yashil shaharlarning iqtisodiy o'sishiga ta'siri.....	293
Xotamov Ibodulla, Najmiddinov Yahyo	
Buxoro viloyatining kichik va o'rta biznesdagi o'rni, viloyatdagi tumanlar faoliyatidan kelib chiqib hududlarni toifalarga ajratish.....	301
Bozorov Ilyos Isomiddinovich	
Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarda ishlab chiqarishning optimal hajmi tahlili	306
Qlichev Baxtiyor Pardaevich, Xoldorov Sardor Umarovich	
Toshkent viloyati fermer xo'jaliklari faoliyatining samaradorligini tanlanma kuzatuvlar asosida statistik tadqiq etish	313
Murodov Jahongir Choriyevich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida sanoat tarmog'i faoliyati samaradorligini statistik baholashning ustuvor yo'nalishlari.....	316
To'raeva Zilola Turg'unovna	
"Yashil" sanoat siyosati – ekologik xavfsizlikni ta'minlashning ustuvor vositasi	320
Muqimov Sherali Axmadali o'g'li	
Raqamli biznes marketingida yashil buxgalteriya hisobining roli: barqaror rivojlanish nuqtai nazaridan qarash.....	327
Allayarov Shamsiddin Amanullayevich, Iskandarov Xurshid Iskandarovich, Yoqubov Madaminbek Abdurahim o'g'li	
Fiskal barqarorlikni ta'minlashda "natijaga yo'naltirilgan budjetlashtirish" uslubidan foydalanish imkoniyatlari.....	333
Kasimova Gulyar Axmatovna, Agzamov Avazxon Talgatovich	
Регулирование занятости и управление трудовыми ресурсами в сфере туризма.....	339
Адылова Зулфия Джавдатовна, Тухтаева Хуршида Фарходовна	
Семь IPO и SPO в экономической истории узбекистана: достижения, проблемы и выводы	346
Чинкулов Кахрамон Равшанович	
Совершенствование учета затрат на производство и калькуляция себестоимости продукции	355
Омонов Шердор Ойбек угли	
Areas of effective use of marketing in the development of foreign economic relations	360
Akhmedov Ikram Akramovich	
Sanoatda oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlashning iqtisodiy masalalari	367
Ismoilova Gulchiroy Tolliboy qizi	

Hududlarni iqtisodiy rivojlanishida investitsiyalar ko'rsatkichi tahlili (Sirdaryo viloyati misolida)	373
Karimqulov Jasur Imomboyevich, Alimova Dilafro'z Tohir qizi	
Raqamli transformatsiya davridagi iqtisodiy o'sishga to'rtinchi sanoat inqilobining ta'siri.....	381
Mirxamidova Zahinabonu Mirxamid qizi	
Investitsion muhit va uning hududlarni iqtisodiyot va ijtimoiy rivojlanishdagi ahamiyati.....	388
Muxamadjanov Shaxriyor Solidjon o'g'li	
Portfel investisiya loyihalarini kreditlashni takomillashtirish.....	395
Ibragimov Gafurjan Axmetovich	
O'zbekistonda kapital bozorini rivojlantirish masalalari	401
Turdieva Uzayda Omirbaevna	
Korxonalarining tashqi savdo faoliyatini rivojlantirishda tijorat banklari faolligini oshirish yo'llari.....	408
Ibragimov Mansur Axmetovich	
Methodological foundations of the quality management system in construction industry enterprises.....	414
Usmanov Ilkhom Achilovich, Buriyev Xakim Toshimovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligini rivojlantirish jarayonini ekonometrik modellashtirishda xorijiy davlatlar tajribasining ahamiyati.....	419
Butanova Dilnoza Rustamovna	
O'zbekistonda qishloq turizmini rivojlantirishda Janubiy Koreya tajribasini o'rganish.....	423
Agzamova Nargiza Gapurovna	
Kimyo sanoatiga innovatsiyalarni joriy etish bo'yicha rivojlangan davlatlar tajribasi.....	427
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich	
Концептуальные основы и перспективы развития деятельности кадастровых служб республики узбекистан на основе интеллектуальных технологий	430
М.К. Валиев, А.Х. Абдуллаев, А.Р. Марахимов, Б.М. Ахмедов	
Mahalliy avtomobil benzini tarkibidagi uglevodород fraksiyalariga ekstragentlarining ta'sirini o'rganish	435
Maxmudov Muxtor Jamolovich, Murtazaev Feruzbek Ismatovich	
Oliy ta'lim muassalaridagi davlat xaridlari tizimining takomillashishi.....	441
Atamuratova Nilufar Yaxshigeldiyevna	
Tijorat banki daromadlari – moliyaviy barqarorlikning omili sifatida.....	446
Umarov Davron Shavkatovich	

WAYS TO EXPAND THE POSITION OF THE LIGHT INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISE IN THE YARN AND KNITWEAR MARKET

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Abstract: This paper explores strategies for expanding the position of light industrial enterprises in the competitive yarn and knitwear market. The study emphasizes the importance of technological innovation, sustainable production practices, and effective marketing strategies in enhancing market competitiveness. By analyzing current trends in the industry, including the rising demand for eco-friendly and high-quality products, the research provides insights into how light industrial enterprises can strengthen their position in both domestic and international markets. The findings suggest that embracing sustainability, improving supply chain management, and adopting advanced technologies are key to achieving long-term success in this sector.

Key words: yarn and knitwear market, light industrial enterprises, technological innovation, sustainability, market competitiveness, supply chain management.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola ip-kalava va trikotaj mahsulotlari bozorida yengil sanoat korxonalarini pozitsiyasini kengaytirish strategiyalarini o'rganadi. Tadqiqotda bozor raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda texnologik innovatsiyalar, barqaror ishlab chiqarish amaliyotlari va samarali marketing strategiyalari muhimligi ta'kidlanadi. Sanoatda kuzatilayotgan dolzarb tendensiyalar, xususan, ekologik toza va yuqori sifatli mahsulotlarga bo'lgan talab ortayotganligi tahlil qilinadi. Maqolada yengil sanoat korxonalarini ichki va xalqaro bozorlarda o'z pozitsiyalarini mustahkamlash yo'llari ko'rsatilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, barqarorlikni qabul qilish, ta'minot zanjirini yaxshilash va ilg'or texnologiyalarni joriy etish ushbu sohada uzoq muddatli muvaffaqiyatga erishishning kaliti hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: ip-kalava va trikotaj bozori, yengil sanoat korxonalarini, texnologik innovatsiyalar, barqarorlik, bozor raqobatbardoshligi, ta'minot zanjiri boshqaruvi.

Аннотация: Данная статья рассматривает стратегии расширения позиций предприятий легкой промышленности на конкурентном рынке пряжи и трикотажных изделий. В исследовании подчеркивается важность технологических инноваций, устойчивых производственных практик и эффективных маркетинговых стратегий для повышения конкурентоспособности на рынке. Анализируются текущие тенденции в отрасли, в том числе растущий спрос на экологически чистую и качественную продукцию. В статье предлагаются пути укрепления позиций предприятий легкой промышленности как на внутреннем, так и на международном рынках. Результаты исследования показывают, что принятие устойчивого развития, улучшение управления цепочками поставок и внедрение передовых технологий являются ключевыми факторами для достижения долгосрочного успеха в данной отрасли.

Ключевые слова: рынок пряжи и трикотажа, предприятия легкой промышленности, технологические инновации, устойчивость, конкурентоспособность рынка, управление цепочками поставок.

INTRODUCTION

The yarn and knitwear market is a rapidly growing segment of the global textile industry, characterized by increasing demand for high-quality, sustainable, and innovative products. Light industrial enterprises play a crucial role in meeting this demand by offering a variety of yarn and knitwear products tailored to diverse consumer needs. However, in a highly competitive market, it is essential for these enterprises to expand their market position by adopting new strategies and innovations.

This paper explores the keyways to enhance the competitive position of light industrial enterprises in the yarn and knitwear market. It discusses the importance of modernizing production processes, integrating advanced technologies, improving product quality, and expanding marketing and distribution channels. Additionally, the paper emphasizes the role of sustainability and the growing consumer preference for eco-friendly products in shaping the future of the yarn and knitwear industry.

By analyzing current market trends and challenges, this study aims to provide insights into how light industrial enterprises can strengthen their position in both domestic and international markets. The findings will offer valuable recommendations for companies seeking to achieve sustainable growth and long-term success in the highly dynamic yarn and knitwear sector.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The global yarn and knitwear market is recognized for its rapid growth and increasing competition, driven by rising consumer demand for innovative and high-quality textile products. To expand their market position, light industrial enterprises must embrace advancements in production processes, marketing strategies, and technological innovation.

Porter and Katz highlight the importance of technological advancements in the yarn and knitwear market, emphasizing how the integration of modern technology improves both the quality and efficiency of production. They argue that businesses that adopt innovative technologies in production, such as automated knitting machines and sustainable fibers, can significantly improve their competitive edge in both domestic and international markets.

Further, Schaltegger and Wagner discuss the growing consumer demand for sustainable and eco-friendly products, which is particularly relevant in the textile industry. Their research suggests that companies incorporating sustainability into their production and marketing strategies not only meet consumer expectations but also foster long-term growth by aligning with global sustainability trends.

Karimov adds a regional perspective, examining the challenges and opportunities for light industrial enterprises in emerging markets. His research on Central Asian textile industries, particularly Uzbekistan, demonstrates how improving supply chain management, increasing export capabilities, and adopting advanced technologies can bolster the position of local enterprises in the global market.

Overall, the literature suggests that for light industrial enterprises to successfully expand their position in the yarn and knitwear market, they must focus on innovation, sustainability, and the efficient use of resources, while also adapting to shifting global consumer preferences.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the implementation of these research works, widely used methods in scientific research methodology were used. When studying the trends of the influence of international financial institutions on the development of states, it is effective to use deduction or induction methods in the order from generality to individuality and vice versa, and the method of abstract-logical thinking is important in the systematic analysis of the process. In the process of scientific analysis, these scientific research methods observation, generalization, grouping, comparison, analysis, and synthesis and analysis methods were widely used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The economic reforms carried out in our country open the door to wide opportunities for production enterprises. As a result of the benefits and preferences given to them, the increase of funds at the disposal of enterprises, the introduction of new forces and the increase of the welfare of the population serve. It is certainly gratifying to see such positive changes in our economy and the economic activity of the country. However, today we all know well that the market economy is an economic system that operates within the framework of the influence of a complex of competition and so-called struggles. In this system, some enterprises work in cooperation with each other, and similar enterprises are in constant competition. In their economic activities, they always meet the needs of the times, the yarn and knitting industry is a competitive and fast-growing market. As companies in this industry seek to expand their position, it is important to understand the current trends and opportunities in the market. In this sense, we analyze the statistics and present strategies that companies can adopt to expand their position in the yarn and knitwear market.

Market trends. According to the latest market research, the global yarn and knitwear market is expected to grow at USD 42.18 billion during 2022-2026 and is expected to grow at a CAGR of 5.77% during the forecast period¹. The growth of the market is primarily due to the increased demand for knitwear by the fashion and textile industries. Additionally, the rise of e-commerce platforms has made it easier for companies to tap into a wider customer base, leading to increased competition in the market.

The yarn and knitting market is a growing industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and various market trends and developments are constantly emerging. In order to expand the company's position in this market, it is very

1 https://www.reportlinker.com/p06359992/Global-Yarn-Market.html?utm_source=GNW

important to be aware of the latest market trends and consumer demands in Uzbekistan. In this paragraph, we present the results of our research on the current market trends of the yarn and knitting industry in Uzbekistan and the strategies that “Daka-Tex” LLC JSC can use to effectively expand its position in the market.

Table 1. Analysis of changes in the development of textile products in the Republic of Uzbekistan² (compared to the previous year, %).

Indicator	2020	2021	2022	2023
Change in Textile Product Development (%)	108.7	104.5	128.5	119.4

Above we use the method of least squares to find the correlation equation.

$$y=kx+b$$

In this correlation equation, we determine the parameters k and b and the correlation coefficient R using the following formulas:

$$k = \frac{n \sum_{i=1}^n x_i y_i - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \sum_{i=1}^n y_i}{n \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n x_i)^2}$$

$$b = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 \sum_{i=1}^n y_i - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \sum_{i=1}^n x_i y_i}{n \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n x_i)^2}$$

$$R = \frac{n \sum_{i=1}^n x_i y_i - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \sum_{i=1}^n y_i}{\sqrt{n \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n x_i)^2} \sqrt{n \sum_{i=1}^n y_i^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n y_i)^2}}$$

Table 2. To find these parameters, we make the following table:

Years	x (notional year)	Y (percent)		x ²	y ²
2020	1	108.7	108.7	1	11815.69
2021	2	104.5	209	4	10920.25
2022	3	128.5	385.5	9	16512.25
2023	4	119.4	477.6	16	14256.36
(sum)	10	461.1	1180.8	30	53504.55

From the above data and formulas, we find the following values:

$$k = \frac{4 \cdot 1180,8 - 10 \cdot 461,1}{4 \cdot 30 - 10 \cdot 10} = 5,61$$

$$b = \frac{30 \cdot 461,1 - 10 \cdot 1180,8}{4 \cdot 30 - 10 \cdot 10} = 101,25$$

$$R = \frac{4 \cdot 1180,8 - 10 \cdot 461,1}{\sqrt{4 \cdot 30 - 10^2} \sqrt{4 \cdot 53504,55 - 461,1^2}} \approx 0,6693;$$

As a result of these calculations:

$$y=5,61x+101,25$$

function, and the correlation coefficient is . Since the given values are proportional to each other and the correlation coefficient is closer to 1 than 0, we can say that the relationship between the trend of the values is closer to the correlation equation we solved.

Of course, there are many factors that affect the market size changes, as well as uncontrollable factors such as Covid-19 and conflicts between some countries. But even in such a situation, we need a market forecast for the development of the enterprise. Through this correlation function, we can forecast the approximate growth rate of textile production in Uzbekistan for the coming years.

² Based on the data of the website <https://www.stat.uz>

Table 3.

Indicator	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024*	2025*
Conditional year (value of x in the formula)	1	2	3	4	5*	6*
Change in Textile Product Development(%)	108.7	104.5	128.5	119.4	129.3*	134.91*

*forecast of correlation function

From this forecast table, we can see that the rate of change in the volume of the textile production market in the following years shows a constant growth trend. And this is important information for the company's plans for the production and sale of products for the next years.

We will consider the current level of development of the yarn and textile products market in the Republic of Uzbekistan according to the following trends:

1. The trend of increasing demand for natural and organic materials.
2. A trend towards sustainable and ethical practices.
3. High demand trend for traditional designs.
4. Developing trend of online commerce.

In Uzbekistan, the demand for natural and organic materials in the yarn and knitting industry is increasing. Consumers are looking for yarn and knitwear made from natural and organic materials such as organic cotton, wool and silk. Companies that use natural and organic materials in their products can address this trend and expand their market position.

Focus on sustainable and ethical practices. Sustainability and ethical practices are important trends in Uzbekistan's yarn and knitwear industry. Consumers are increasingly aware of the environmental impact of their purchases and are looking for sustainable and ethical products. Companies that adopt sustainable practices and offer sustainable products are more likely to attract environmentally conscious consumers and expand their market position.

High demand for traditional designs. Traditional designs are popular in the yarn and knitting market of Uzbekistan. Consumers are looking for traditional and unique designs that reflect the country's cultural heritage. Companies that offer products with traditional designs and patterns can tap into this trend and expand their market position.

Growing online commerce. The growth of e-commerce has led to increased demand for online shopping opportunities in the yarn and knitwear market in Uzbekistan. Companies with a strong online presence, including user-friendly websites and active social media accounts, can reach a wider audience and expand their market position.

Our recommended strategies for expanding the position of "Daka-Tex" LLC in the yarn and knitwear market in the Republic of Uzbekistan:

In order to effectively expand the position and position of Daka-Tex LLC in the market of Uzbekistan, it is important to conduct market research and analysis in order to determine current trends and consumer requirements. This helps the business to adapt its products and services to meet these demands and attract the target audience.

Product innovation. Innovation is the key to expanding the place and position of "Daka-Tex" LLC in the market of Uzbekistan. Companies that constantly innovate and offer new and exciting products can differentiate themselves from the competition and attract consumers who are looking for unique and customized products.

Offer national-traditional designs. Offering yarn and knitted products with national-traditional designs and patterns allows "Daka-Tex" LLC to appeal to the cultural heritage of Uzbekistan and expand its position in the market. Cooperation with local designers and craftsmen helps the enterprise to incorporate national-traditional designs into its products.

Diversification of product offerings. In today's highly competitive environment, companies in the yarn and knitwear industry must be creative and innovative to expand their position. Diversification of product offerings is a strategy that helps Daka-Tex LLC gain a competitive advantage, meet changing customer demands, and ultimately expand its market position.

Advantages of diversification:

1. Increase in customer base. By offering a wider range of products, companies can attract a diverse customer base. For example, a company that previously only offered yarn for knitwear can expand to offer yarn for home decor, attracting customers interested in crocheting rugs or wall hangings.

Expanding distribution channels can provide several benefits for Daka-Tex LLC, including market expansion, improved customer service, and competitive advantage. A business can use strategies such as identifying new channels, evaluating logistics and infrastructure, developing relationships with partners, and investing in technology to effectively expand its distribution reach. By effectively delivering products to customers and entering new markets, the enterprise gains a wide informational environment and the opportunity to expand its position in the market. Embracing sustainability is critical for Daka-Tex LLC to expand its position and achieve long-term success. Using sustainable materials, reducing waste, by adopting sustainable manufacturing practices and educating customers, companies can significantly reduce their environmental impact and increase their reputation as environmentally responsible companies. By tapping into this growing market segment of environmentally conscious consumers, companies can increase their sales and profits and achieve long-term success.

Being aware of market trends and consumer demands in Uzbekistan is important in expanding the company's position and position in the yarn and knitwear market. By adopting sustainable practices, offering traditional designs, having a strong online presence, and using natural and organic materials, Daka-Tex LLC can address current market trends in Uzbekistan and expand its market position. Analyzing statistical data and understanding market trends, conducting research and analysis, innovating products, collaborating with local designers and artisans also give the enterprise a competitive advantage.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In summary, expanding the market position of light industrial enterprises within the yarn and knitwear industry necessitates a comprehensive and strategic approach. The research demonstrates that embracing technological advancements, such as automated production systems and the use of sustainable materials, can significantly enhance production efficiency and product quality. By focusing on innovation, companies can meet the rising consumer demand for eco-friendly and ethically sourced products, which is becoming a key factor in gaining a competitive advantage in both domestic and international markets.

Moreover, improving supply chain management plays a critical role in ensuring that enterprises can efficiently deliver products to market, reduce costs, and maintain high levels of quality. The integration of advanced logistics and inventory management systems enables companies to optimize their operations and respond swiftly to market changes. Additionally, adopting modern marketing strategies, including digital marketing and brand differentiation, helps light industrial enterprises reach a broader audience and build stronger relationships with customers.

The study also underscores the importance of aligning business practices with global trends in sustainability and corporate social responsibility. As consumers become more environmentally conscious, enterprises that actively promote their commitment to sustainable practices are more likely to secure long-term loyalty and market share.

In conclusion, for light industrial enterprises to successfully expand their position in the highly competitive yarn and knitwear market, they must adopt a holistic approach that includes innovation, sustainability, supply chain optimization, and modern marketing practices. These combined efforts will not only strengthen their competitive edge but also ensure long-term growth and success in the rapidly evolving global marketplace.

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